

PRIMITIVE TRIBES ACCESS TO HEALTH CARE IN TAMIL NADU : A SOCIAL EXCLUSION PERSPECTIVE

Easwaran Kanagaraj*

Abstract: *The present paper attempts to assess the access of primitive tribes to health care in Tamil Nadu from the perspective of social exclusion. The paper is based on the primary data collected through structured household interview schedule from the primitive tribes in the Nilgiris, Tamil Nadu. The study reveals the significant variation in the household access to health care among the four tribes. The patterns and levels of access to health care of the households of non-scheduled primitive tribe of Badaga were significantly different from those of scheduled tribes of Kota, Irula and Kurumba. Contrary to expectations, the scheduled primitive tribal households have greater access to the health care institutions as compared to the non-scheduled tribe, the Badaga. This could be attributed mainly to access of the former to health care provided by Non-Governmental organisations (NGOs). Exclusion in the context of PTGs in health care is found to occur due to hierarchy in the quality of health care rather due to availability of them to the scheduled primitive tribal households. The study draws the attention of the Government towards improvement of quality of health care in the tribal areas through adequate personnel, infrastructure and promoting sustainable development. The role of grass root organisations and social workers in mobilisation of STs on their rights is also emphasised.*

INTRODUCTION

Schedule Tribes (STs) constitute one of the socially excluded sections of Indian society for centuries. The most excluded and underdeveloped among them are the numerically small primitive tribal groups (PTGs). Government of India recognised the need for focussing on these marginalised section of STs first in 1975-76 and thereafter in 1993. Ever since, the poorest of poor amongst the STs were called Primitive Tribal Groups (PTGs). The Government of India has followed a threefold criterion for identification of

such PTGs. They are - (1) at pre-agricultural level of technology, (2) with very low level of literacy; and (3) having a declining or stagnant population. Based on the above mentioned criteria, 75 tribal communities were identified as PTGs spread over what are now 17 States and one UT.¹ The national five-year plans and ongoing tribal sub plan (TSP) approach are focussing on the development of primitive tribal groups (PTGs). In fact, the Government of India has conceded that the problem of extinction of primitive tribes is one of the persisting problems of tribals in the tenth plan.^a

^a In the tenth plan document the Government of India pointed out certain unresolved issues and persisting problems with regard to tribal population of the country, which warrant immediate attention of state and non-state actors. The unresolved issues in tribal development planning according to Government of India (1992) are displacement of tribals, tribal land alienation, indebtedness, shifting cultivation, and deprivation of forest rights while the persisting problems are low literacy and high drop-out rates, inadequate and inaccessible health services, nutritional deficiencies and diseases, lack of adequate irrigation facilities, extreme/abject poverty, endangering of intellectual rights, crimes/atrocities against STs, neglect of forest villages, extinction of primitive tribal groups, ineffective implementation of PESA, 1996, and routinised mechanism of TSP.

* Department of Social Work, Mizoram University, Aizawl 796 004.
E-mail: mekanagaraj@gmail.com

According to the 2001 Census the PTGs are about 1.32 million population and constitute 1.57 percent of the total population of the country. The ST population in Tamil Nadu is 6, 51,321 and constitutes over 1 per cent of the population of the state as per the 2001 census. In the state, there are 36 STs, of which 6 viz., Toda, Kota, Kurumbas, Irular, Paniyan and Kattunayakan are PTGs. The PTGs form 33 per cent of the total ST population in the state as per the 2001 census. Health is one of the components of standard of living. It is often construed as one of the basic needs and one of the components of human development.² Access to Health care is considered as one of the components of social inclusion and means of tribal integration. Hence, tribal health has been one of the major areas of tribal studies and there is a copious literature on the same in India. Health status of the tribes in different geographic zones has been studied and documented by a number of social science scientist from varied theoretical perspectives and methodological orientations.

Standard demographic indicators like life expectancy,² fertility and mortality (for instance³ were used to show the relatively poor health status of tribals. There are studies which focus on the health disorders among the tribes. For example Zanver *et al.* (1998) attempted to assess the influence of family income, parental occupation and literacy on prevalence of nutritional disorders among tribal preschool children in Maharastra.⁴ Basu (1994) reported two genetic disorders viz. sickle cell anaemia and Glucose-6-Phosphate Enzyme Deficiency widely

prevalent among the ST population in India.^{5,6}

There are some studies, which focus on the health care utilisation among the tribal households.⁷⁻¹⁰ Rani Gopal (1996) reported improvement of tribal health status over the years.¹¹ Hiramani (1997) undertook a study to examine preventive and curative health behaviour of tribal people and their social and cultural attributes associated covering three states. He found that income, media exposure, and number of episodes in the households were positively related with the utilization of health care serves from primary health centre and sub centre among the tribals.¹² Basu (1998) felt that in spite of expansion of health facilities in tribal area and government's efforts to improve health situation of the tribals, hardly any significant impact on the important health indicators of tribal people was achieved.⁷ He was of the opinion that the simple linear expansion of the existing health care delivery system is not appropriate to improve health and family welfare of tribal population. Instead, he suggested the location of health facilities should be as per local needs depending on geographical and population consideration, resources and manpower availability. Access to health care has also been discussed in the literature on social exclusion separately or as a sub-component of social services along with education.¹³

In spite of existence of copious literature on health in India, a few studies address the health problems of numerically small primitive tribes.¹⁴ In the context of the PTGs, the inter-tribal

variation in the patterns and levels of access of households to health care has not been adequately probed into. The present study focuses on these issues in the context of Tamil Nadu from theoretical perspective of social exclusion. It compares the levels and patterns of access to health care among households Scheduled primitive tribe of Badaga and scheduled tribes of Kota, Kurumba and Irula. These primitive tribes are at different economic stages. The non scheduled tribe of Badaga were settled agriculturalists. The scheduled primitive tribes were different in their traditional occupations which are mostly continued by them till today. Kotas were artisans mainly serving the other tribes in the Nilgiris while Kurumba were hunters and food gatherers while the Irula were hill cultivators.

The paper is presented in four sections. The first section is devoted to discuss the theoretical perspective. The second section is devoted to discuss various aspects of the methodology followed. In the fourth section, the results are discussed while the fifth section presents the concluding observations.

Social Exclusion Framework

In this section the theoretical framework of social exclusion as well as issues in their application has been discussed. The concept of social exclusion has originated in France and has been introduced into British and other debates. According to de Haan (1998) it has spread European Union (EU) channels: funding for social insertion via the European social fund, the European Anti poverty Network, the second and third anti poverty

programmes, and for developing countries, and research funds.¹⁵

Social exclusion has been conceptualised in different paradigms, which are broadly classified by Silver (1994) as mainstream sociological models (solidarity, specialisation, and monopoly) and organic models (Christian democratic, state corporatist, and consociational).¹⁶ According to her in solidarity paradigm dominant in France, exclusion is the rupture of social bond between the individual and society that is cultural and moral. The social order is conceived as external, moral and normative, rather than grounded in individual, group or class interests. A national consensus, collective conscience or general will, binds the individual to the larger society through vertically inter-related mediating institutions. Cultural boundaries give rise to socially constructed dualistic categories of ordering the world, declining the poor, unemployed and ethnic minorities as deviant outsiders. In the specialization, dominant in Britain social differentiation, exclusion reflects discrimination. Social differentiation of spheres should not produce hierarchically ordered social categories if the "excluded" individuals are free to move across the boundaries and in spheres of social life governed by different principles are kept legally separate. The third paradigm perceives exclusion as a consequence of the formation of group monopolies. Powerful groups, often with distinctive cultural identities and institutions, restrict the access of outsiders to valued resources through a process of "social closure."

Silver (1994) clarified that mainstream sociological models (paradigms) of social exclusion as ideal typical i.e. models to observe social reality rather than the reality itself.¹⁶ Each model conceives of exclusion as a social relationship between the excluded and the included. These approaches are applicable to both micro and macro level sociological analysis. The most important clarification on these paradigms, she makes is that of the distinction between them and the organic models of social integration. The organic models of integration are concerned with construction of social order based on functional, regional, or primordial groups. Silver finds three major streams of thought in organic approaches to integration viz., Christian democratic (societal neo-corporatist); state corporatist; and consociational. According to her though they differ in their emphasis on individual rights, they all reject extreme individualism and collectivism. But, they reflect the principles of 'community' and 'subsidiarity'.¹⁷

Silver (1995) favours the mainstream sociological models of social integration viz. solidarity, specialization, and monopoly over the organic models as the former attributes to greater scope and autonomy to civil society relative to the state and market than do the latter paradigms.¹⁷ She contends that the organic-statist integration itself exclusionary and there is no logic behind their recognition of vertical functional associations based on primordial identities over the horizontal, decentralized participatory and membership associations.¹⁷

The major theoretical question here is which paradigm suitable to study the micro context of the primitive tribes in India. In the present study, monopoly paradigm has been found to have better interpretative power as the economic stage varies across the primitive tribes in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

The present study is cross sectional in nature and based on the primary data collected through field survey with structured household interview schedule and the household is the unit. The quantitative data collected was supplemented with qualitative data collected through key informant interviews with the leaders and knowledgeable persons of the primitive tribes chosen. Though qualitative data is used, the present study is by and large quantitative in its orientation.

In the present study, a multistage sampling procedure has been followed in the selection of the district, block, tribes, hamlets and households. The first stage is the choice of district. The primitive tribes in Tamil Nadu include six tribes viz., Toda, Kota, Kurumbas, Irular, Paniyan and Kattunayakan forming 31.49 per cent of the total tribal population in Tamil Nadu. In view of the fact that all these tribes are living in the Nilgiris, the district was chosen for the present micro level study. The second stage of sampling is the selection of block. In the Nilgiris district, there are four administrative blocks, viz., Udhamandalam, Coonoor, Kotagiri and Gudalure. Among these blocks, Gudalur and Kotagiri had high concentration of Tribal population (5-

10%). In view of these criteria of numerical strength and ST population concentration, the Kotagiri block was chosen for the study. Selection of the Tribes forms the third stage of sampling. In the Kotagiri block, five primitive tribes are concentrated. In two ways they may be classified. Firstly, based on their inclusion in ST list, they can be classified as the scheduled primitive tribes of Toda, Kota, Kurumba and Irula and the non-scheduled primitive tribe of the Badaga. Secondly, on the basis of their location on the Nilgiris Mountains, these tribes are generally classified as the massif tribes and sub-tropical tribes. The massif tribes of the Toda, Badaga and Kota are racially different from the sub-tropical tribes the Kurumba and Irula. The former are fair while the latter are dark in complexion and have differential racial affinity.¹⁸ Apart from racial difference, the climate, soil, rainfall and thus the natural resource endowment all are favourable to the tribes on the massif. Among the five primitive tribes the non-scheduled tribe Badaga and scheduled tribes of Kota, Kurumba and Irula were chosen. This is mainly because the concentration of Toda is not sufficient for sampling i.e. they live in only one-hamlet (Mund) constituting around 20 households. As statistical analysis of quantitative data warrants large sample, the Toda was excluded from the sample.

Having chosen the tribes, the next stage of selection is that of hamlets. One hamlet to represent each of the four tribes was chosen. Kannerimukku, Pudukkotagiri, Banagudi and Kunjappanai were the four hamlets chosen to represent the four primitive tribes the Badaga, Kota, Kurumba and

Irula respectively. The choice was made after having discussions with the NGO workers, Government grass root level workers, tribal leaders and making a number of visits to the settlements. It was ensured that the socio economic conditions of the village chosen would reflect the general conditions of the particular tribe.

The last stage is the selection of the households. Separate lists of the heads of the households of the four hamlets were prepared in consultation with the key informants of each of the hamlet. From the lists of the four hamlets one half of the households from each of the hamlet, were chosen randomly using Tippets table of random numbers with replacement of the unit chosen. There was no data on the population of households in each of the four tribes was not available either from government or NGOs. Hence, in determination of sample size no standard formula was used. On the other hand, the sample size was arrived at, to ensure large sample in each of the four tribes, as it is needed for analysis of quantitative data. Thus the sample size arrived for Badaga, Kota, Kurumba and Irula were 72, 32, 30 and 38 respectively.

A structured household interview schedule was employed to collect primary data from the sample households. The schedule included demographic, social, economic and political information of each of the households. The schedule was prepared after an intensive pilot study in the tribal hamlets. The structured interview schedule was pre tested and finalised in the light of it. The pilot study helped the research to contextualise the theoretical frameworks, conceptualise

and operationalise the constructs as per the demands of micro level tribal reality. The schedule was administered through personal interviews with most knowledgeable person of the household chosen. The personal interview ranged between 30 to 45 minutes normally. The fieldwork was conducted during the months of January and February 2003 and the reference period was the agricultural year 2002.

The collected data was processed and analysed with computer software. SPSS Software (Version 11.0) was used to analyse the data. Data analysis was done with simple averages, ranks, one-way ANOVA and Spearman's rho. ANOVA with Least Square Difference (LSD) has been used to analyse the intertribal variations in the levels of access to health care while Spearman's rank correlation coefficients (rho) were computed to assess the significance of intertribal differences in their patterns.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Access to health care has always been discussed in the literature on social exclusion separately or as a sub-component of social services along with education. In the present study the pattern of access to health care of the tribal households has been measured in terms of the frequency of visits of the members of household to various health care institutions. In Nilgiris, the major agents promoting health care include Government, Private Sector, NGOs, Christian Missionaries, and Indigenous Medical Practitioners. Government or public health care centres, sub centres and public hospitals constitute a major

institutional network providing health care services to the people including tribals in the Nilgiris as elsewhere in India. Private hospitals ranging from dispensaries of individual doctors to huge hospitals with sophisticated medical infrastructure and specialist medical and paramedical professionals who are aiming at profit also function in the Nilgiris catering the health care needs of those are able and willing to pay. The Christian Missionaries run huge hospitals with sophisticated infrastructure and trained medical personnel in the major towns of the Nilgiris. The voluntary organizations or NGOs come next to the missionaries in terms of resources, infrastructure and quality of personnel. Yet, their mobile services and camps in the remote inaccessible tribal hamlets on the one hand and dispensaries in those places make them more accessible to the tribal masses. Tribals have been well known for their own indigenous medical practices and magic and witchcraft. Especially in the Nilgiris the Kurumba have been popular for this over centuries.

The access to health care institutions was assessed for each of the agency with the help of a 4-point scale viz., always, mostly, sometimes and never. They were assigned 3,2,1 and 0 scores respectively. The total of the scores on each of these six institutions have been obtained at household level and this summary measure is treated as household access to health care. The household scores of the six institutions were analysed with the help of simple averages, and their mean scores were ranked. To study the significance of differences in the patterns of health care the ranks of the institutions across the four tribes were analysed with

Spearman's rho. Further, ANOVA has been used to analyse the intertribal variations in the levels of access to health care. Table 1 presents the means, standard deviations (SD), ranks as well as the results of ANOVA while Table 2 presents the Spearman's inter correlation matrix of ranks of health care institutions among different tribes.

Patterns of Access to Health Care

The basic question the present paper addresses is that weather there is any

differences in the patterns of household access to health care among the primitive tribes in Tamil Nadu. The results analysis of Spearman's rho coefficients clearly shows the significant intertribal variation in the patterns of access to health care. The pattern of access to health care differs significantly between the non-scheduled and scheduled primitive tribes. The pattern of access of scheduled primitive tribes of Kota, Kurumba and Irula to health care was significantly different from that of non-scheduled primitive tribe

Table 1: Access to Institutions of Health Care: Mean Scores and Ranks

Sl.No	Institution	Tribe				Total N = 172
		Badaga n = 72	Kota n = 32	Kurumba n = 30	Irula n = 38	
1	Private Hospital	1.88 ± 0.9 (1)	0.94 ± 0.8 (2)	0.43 ± 0.6 (4)	0.66 ± 0.7 (3)	1.18 ± 1.0 (1)
2	Hospital of NGO	0.00 ± 0.0 (6)	2.13 ± 0.8 (1)	1.90 ± 0.8 (1)	2.03 ± 0.8 (1)	1.17 ± 1.1 (2)
3	Government Public Hospital	1.17 ± 0.8 (2)	0.72 ± 0.6 (3)	1.00 ± 0.5 (2)	0.66 ± 0.5 (2)	0.94 ± 0.7 (3)
4	Primary Health Centre	0.44 ± 0.6 (3)	0.09 ± 0.3 (4)	0.53 ± 0.5 (3)	0.66 ± 0.7 (4)	0.44 ± 0.6 (4)
5	Indigenous Medicinal Practice	0.06 ± 0.2 (4)	0.03 ± 0.2 (5)	0.20 ± 0.5 (5)	0.39 ± 0.5 (5)	0.15 ± 0.4 (5)
6	Christian Missionary Hospital	0.04 ± 0.2 (5)	0.00 ± 0.0 (6)	0.00 ± 0.0 (6)	0.00 ± 0.2 (6)	0.02 ± 0.2 (6)
	Access to Health Care	3.53 ± 0.7	3.88 ^a ± 0.6	3.87 ^a ± 0.6	4.00 ^a ± 0.6	3.76 ± 0.7
	F	10.87 ^{**}				

Source: Computed Figures in parentheses are ranks Mean ± S.D

* Significant at 5% level ** Significant at 1% level

Note: Means with common superscripts not significantly different

Table 2 :Differences in Pattern of Access to Health Care: Spearman's rho(N=6)

Tribe	Badaga	Kota	Kurumba	Irula	Total
Badaga	1	0.14	-0.03	0.09	0.43
Kota	0.14	1	0.83*	0.94**	0.94**
Kurumba	-0.03	0.83*	1	0.94**	0.66
Irula	0.09	0.94**	0.94**	1	0.83**
Total	0.43	0.94**	0.66	0.83**	1

Source: Computed * Significant at 5% level ** Significant at 1% level

of Badaga. The Spearman's rho coefficients of Badaga with Kota (0.14), Irula (-0.03), Kurumba (0.09) were at all not significant even at 5 percent level. On the other hand, there is no significant difference among the scheduled tribes of Kota, Kurumba, and Irula. The computed rho coefficients of ranks of health care access scores between Kota and Irula (0.94), Kota and Kurumba (0.83), Irula and Kurumba (0.94) were positive and significant at 5 percent level (Table 2).

The NGO hospitals was the primary source of health care and treatment of chronic as well as acute diseases for the Kota, the Kurumba, and the Irula the three scheduled primitive tribes. On the contrary, for the Badaga the primary source of health care was the private hospitals. The government hospitals, as the second most prominent source of treatment to the Badaga, the Kurumba and the Irula households, while for the Kota it was private hospitals. Of course the Government hospital was third in the order of preference of the Kota. Likewise the Irula household's third preference was the private hospitals. The role of Christian Missionaries in the promotion of tribal health was negligible among the tribes and it was in the last position among all the tribes (Table 1).

Level of Access to Health Care

The next question that is considered here is that of intertribal variation in the household's access to health care. The results of one-way ANOVA clearly demonstrate the significant differences in the levels of access to health care among the PTGs. The computed F ratio (10.87) for the access score was significant at 1

percent level. The analysis of mean difference in the household health care access score with least square difference (LSD) test reveals the significant difference between the non-scheduled tribe of Badaga on the one hand and the scheduled tribes on the other. On average, the households of scheduled primitive tribes of Kota (3.88), Irula (3.87) and Kurumba (4.00) have significantly greater access score as compared to the Badaga (3.53), the non-scheduled primitive tribe. Further, among the households of scheduled primitive tribes of Kota, Irula, and Kurumba, the difference in the access score was not even significant at 5 percent level (Table 1).

Interestingly, all the tribes had high level of access to health care. The household average of the overall access score of all the four tribes were greater than 3. It seems that the tribals are utilizing the different agencies for fulfilment of their health care needs and they were not left with untreated when they suffer from diseases. The various agencies at work have some how successful in extending the health care to all the tribal households. The comparison of the four tribes according to their access scores to the specific institutions further reveals the variations in the access to health care. There was considerable variation in the utilisation of health care among the four tribes. The Irula had the highest access score (4.00) closely followed by the Kota (3.88), the Kurumba (3.87) and the Badaga (3.53). The greater access of the scheduled tribes to the health care institutions over the non-scheduled tribe the Badaga was mainly

due to their access to health care by voluntary organisations.

The access to private hospital was highest to the Badaga (1.88) followed by the Kota (0.94) the Irula (0.66) and the Kurumba (0.43). The greater access to private health care to the Badaga and the Kota over the Kurumba and the Irula could be attributed to their better economic standing as well as health awareness. As regards the NGO Hospitals, the Badaga had no access, while among the three scheduled tribes the Kota (2.13) had greater access closely followed by the Irula (2.03) and the Kurumba (1.90). The Badaga had no access to NGO hospitals because they were excluded from the Scheduled Tribe in the post independence period. The three scheduled tribes it seems that most of the times had gone for treatment in the NGO Hospitals. It was observed in the field that the members of the Kota, the Irula and the Kurumba mostly visit the hospitals of Nilgiris Adivasi Welfare Association (NAWA) near most of the tribal settlements. Besides, the NAWA also provides mobile health care services periodically to the tribes.

As regards the government hospitals, the Badaga households had greater access (1.17) followed by the Kurumba (1.00), the Kota (0.72) and the Irula (0.66). On the contrary, the Irula households (0.66) had greater utilization of the Government's Primary health centres and sub centres followed by the Kurumba (0.53), the Badaga (0.44) and the Kota (0.09) respectively. The least utilization of the primary health centres by the Kota was mainly due to their proximity

to the health centres of NGO hospitals on the one hand and their accessibility to private sector health care.

Only the Kurumba and the Irula households utilized the indigenous health practitioners, while the Badaga and the Kota households made little use of it. Between the sub-tropical primitive tribes, the Irula (0.20) had slightly greater use of the native health practitioners over the Kurumba (0.39). The non-utilization of traditional tribal medicine by the Kota was due to two major reasons. Firstly, their tribesmen have not been traditionally engaged in such art. Secondly, they had greater access to advanced allopathic medical system provided by NAWA hospitals. The continuity of usage of tribal medicine by the Kurumba and the Irula was mainly because it is interwoven with their culture and belief system. It could also be attributed to the easy availability of these practitioners in the villages of the Kurumba and the Irula tribes and their cheaper cost. It is unfortunate to note that the tribal medicine practice widely prevalent among the Badaga community in the past is no where in existence or use. The poor situation is mainly due to the promotion of modern medicine by the Government authorities on the one hand and the neglect of tribal and traditional folk medicine as unscientific and blind faith by the agencies of modernisation without actually testing their utility and effectiveness. The Christian Missionaries, whose role in promoting the health care elsewhere lauded, perceptibly play an insignificant role among the primitive tribes of the Nilgiris. The wide opposition to conversion to Christianity or

proselytisation by the tribal people of the Nilgiris especially their leaders forbade the missionaries to extend their health services.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

At the outset the paper has raised two major interrelated questions in the context of primitive tribes of Tamil Nadu. They pertain to the PTGs level and patterns of access to health care. Social Exclusion framework has been used to identify the agencies contributing access as well as the levels. Though, invariably, the primitive tribal households have high level of access to health care, those belonging to scheduled tribes of Kota Kurumba and Irula had greater access to health care as compared to those of the non-scheduled tribe of Badaga. The former three tribes access the free health care services of NGOs and rely mainly on them while for the latter the main source was private health care for which they pay. In spite of the greater access, the quality of health care provided to the scheduled tribes has been perceived by the leaders as poor and the tribal leaders often complain the inadequacy of the medicine and medical staff in the public hospitals and primary health centres. Such criticisms were even levelled against the NGO sector, the adequacy of whose services in the recent decade (era of LPG) are doubtful in the perception of the tribal leaders.

In the light of the findings of the present study, it can be argued that the exclusion in health care occurs mainly because of the correspondence between hierarchy in the quality of health care and

economic stage of tribe. The households of predominantly agricultural tribe (non-scheduled primitive tribe) of Badaga were found to have access to quality private health care while the scheduled tribes rely on the NGO sector as well as sub centres whose quality was questioned by the tribal people. Unfortunately, the matter of fact is that the public intervention in health care could not transcend the economic stage of the tribes. Thus, the main challenge before the policy makers, grass root organisations and social workers in this context of the PTGs at least in Tamil Nadu is not actually improving the access; rather it is on improvement of the quality of health care provided to the tribal masses as well as promoting sustainable development through income generation activities. The State and Central Governments can accomplish this by providing adequate personnel and infrastructure for health care in the tribal areas. In this connection, it is also suggested that the NGOs with high degree of commitment, capacity, and professionalism need to be supported with adequate Government grants and funds for providing health care as well as engaging in sustainable income generation. The social workers, grass root organisations have to come forward towards mobilising, organising and advocating for the tribal right to quality health care and livelihood.

Towards improving the health care among the tribes, there is also a need for promoting indigenous medicine systems among the tribes especially the Kurumbas and Irulas. Efforts for providing adequate training, financial support and

conduct of scientific research can be made by Government agencies, academic institutions, and NGOs individually or in collaboration. The NGOs and social workers need to mobilise, organise, train and promote network among the practitioners of tribal medicine towards sustaining these systems.

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